

ANALYTICAL PREDICTIONS RELATING APPLIED LOADS TO RESIDUAL
PROPERTIES OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

An incremental dynamic response formulation is presented which models damage progression on a ply-by-ply basis. A direct integration algorithm is used and equilibrium iterations are performed within each incremental time step. Stress based failure criteria are utilized to differentiate between various failure modes including fiber fracture, matrix cracking and delamination. A shear deformable finite element formulation provides the framework for obtaining numerical solutions. A unique feature in the approach is the use of equilibrium equations to obtain the transverse stresses in determining whether or not delamination occurs during response. Equilibrium equations are numerically approximated to represent shear free conditions at the upper and lower boundaries of the laminate, as well as at the boundaries of a sub-set of delaminated plies. This approach gives a reasonably realistic transverse stress distribution in determining whether or not stress criteria have been violated, and thus affects modification of shear moduli as damage progresses. Eigensolutions are obtained and compared for undamaged and damaged models. Results are presented for laminated beam and plate geometries. Reference is also made to an ongoing experimental program aimed at improving the damage criteria so that stiffness reduction can be better represented as well as variations in damping characteristics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composites will become more significant in many aerospace applications, i.e., they will be more widely utilized as primary load-bearing structures. Their use has increased in recent years, and in space composites should provide much of the primary structure for the space station. A methodology is needed to predict the residual properties and performance of such structures for expected loading conditions. Results herein presented are part of an ongoing research effort aimed at developing the sensitivity criteria needed to relate various combinations of damage to residual properties. These criteria could be used to develop parametric curves relating loading conditions to changes in dynamic characteristics, and thus indirectly to expected structural integrity.

Laminates are presently designed on the basis of general failure criteria, e.g., that given by Tsai-Wu (1). Soni (2) employed a number of commonly used general failure criteria in predicting first and last ply failures for a range of laminate geometries. General failure criteria have the disadvantage that they do not differentiate between failure modes. A stress based failure criteria developed by Hashin (3) differentiates between fiber and matrix failure modes, in tension and compression, for unidirectional composites. Lee (4) used a similar approach in presenting similar stress criteria to differentiate a delamination failure from the other modes. Talreja (5) has developed an internal state variable representation of damage and has applied it in studying the effects of matrix cracking on stiffness reduction. His approach could be applied to representing other forms of damage and in developing relationships between damage and variations in moduli and Poisson's ratio. Fiber microbuckling criteria have been developed by several researchers, e.g., Greszczuk (6), Hahn and Williams (7), and more recently by Wass et.al. (8).

The stress based criteria reported in (3,4) have been incorporated by Ochoa and Engblom (9) as damage conditions in a shear deformable finite element formulation. The intent is to model the progression of damage in laminated composite structures under static loads. Engblom and Havelka (10) have extended the incremental formulation in the treatment of damage associated with transient dynamic loading. These finite element

based models reduce the moduli and Poisson's ratio in appropriate plies on the basis of stress criteria. Stress redistribution is accounted for by performing equilibrium iterations throughout the incremental procedure. In the present work, refinements in transverse stress variation are incorporated to better represent delamination between plies. While the internal state variable formulation is not presently incorporated in the numerical model, some discussion is given on extending the present approach and on a related experimental program.

2. NUMERICAL MODELING

A shear deformable finite element formulation provides the basis for obtaining both the transient response and associated residual properties of damaged laminated composite structures. Piecewise smooth stress-based failure criteria (3,4) are utilized to differentiate between the damage modes occurring in different plies. The Newmark direct integration method is used to obtain the incremental numerical solutions. Force equilibrium iterations are performed in each increment to represent the stress redistributions associated with the progression of damage.

An eight-noded, shear deformable plate finite element formulation (9,10) provides the mathematical foundation for the model. Ply-by-ply integration is performed to determine stiffness properties, and thus to account for damage at the ply level. Constitutive equations are solved to obtain the in-plane stresses within the plies. The transverse interlaminar stresses, however, are obtained by integrating the equilibrium equations. This approach provides computational efficiencies for thin to moderately thick composites.

Additional notes on the specifics of the solution procedure are useful here. When the iterative procedure detects damage within a ply, the material matrix is modified at the ply level. Appropriate terms in the material matrix are modified as damage develops to reflect stiffness reductions and stress redistribution. This procedure presently involves zeroing out constitutive terms. A improved approach would involve combining an internal state variable representation of damage with stress criteria. The material matrix $[D]$ in a particular layer has the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ d_{21} & d_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

where the d_{ij} stiffness terms involve the orthotropic ply moduli E_{11} , E_{22} , and G_{12} as well as Poisson's ratio ν_{12} . Appropriate terms in the material matrix are reduced to zero to represent the lost extensional and shear stiffness. When fiber failure occurs, the d_{11} , d_{12} , d_{33} and d_{44} terms are set to zero thus representing stiffness and shear modes of the fiber. When matrix failure is predicted, the d_{12} , d_{22} , d_{44} and d_{55} terms are reduced to zero. When the stress criteria predict delamination, the d_{44} and d_{55} terms are set to zero. The updated material matrix is then used in the computational procedure to recalculate stresses within damaged layers. As damage accumulates, appropriate terms are continuously modified to account for variations in load carrying capability. Equilibrium iterations serve to assure that stresses are redistributed to the undamaged layers.

A complexity in realistically modeling is the effect of load cycling, i.e., after tensile fiber failure, tensile matrix failure or delamination, subsequent compression loading would exhibit some residual stiffness. This is a phenomenon that needs experimental investigation because it strongly influences characteristics of the transient dynamic response exhibited by a laminated composite structure, i.e., the frequency and amplitude of response. In the present computational approach, compression after a given type of failure assumes that a fraction α_i of the original stiffness is retained. For example,

the modified material matrix after a tensile fiber failure has the form

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

and when this particular layer goes back into compression, the material matrix becomes

$$\begin{bmatrix} \alpha_1 d_{11} & \alpha_1 d_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha_1 d_{12} & d_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 d_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \alpha_1 d_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

Different fractions of residual stiffness can be assumed for different damage modes. A fractional value of $\alpha_i=0$ assumes that there is no residual compressive stiffness in a particular mode of damage. After damage occurs in a ply, the matrices given above are alternatively used to represent stiffness as the stresses vary between tensile and compressive values. Note that accurate values of residual stiffness can only be defined on the basis of extensive experimentation.

Another aspect of modeling damage relates to use of the equilibrium equations to obtain the interlaminar stresses when a delamination is predicted. A delamination is represented as a reduction in the shear moduli in a ply or in a sub-set of plies on the basis of the failure stress criteria. Kinematics of the plate element are maintained; so that, the true displacement distribution through the element can not be represented exactly. A more accurate kinematical model would layer elements through-the-thickness of the laminate and allow constraints between elements to become relaxed as the delamination progressed. Because the present formulation utilizes simply one element in the thickness direction, a less exact approach is formulated. The equilibrium equations are integrated based on assuming shear free surfaces at the upper and lower surfaces of the laminate, and additionally, shear free surfaces at the boundaries of a delaminated sub-set of layers. This provides a more realistic transverse stress distribution in determining whether or not stress criteria have been violated and whether or not to modify the shear moduli. Change in the shear stress τ_{xz} across the j^{th} layer is given as

$$\Delta \tau_{xz_j} = - \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} \right)_j \Delta z_j \quad (1)$$

where subscripts x and y refer to coordinates in the plane of the laminate while z is in the transverse or thickness direction. σ_x and τ_{xy} represent normal and shear stress in the plane of the ply, and Δz_j represents thickness of the jth ply. A similar equilibrium equation can be written in numerical form for the change in shear stress τ_{yz} . The right hand side of equation (1) is obtained by taking derivatives of smoothing functions that represent the constitutive stresses, i.e., $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}$. A more concise notation involves representing the right hand side of (1) as I_{xz_j} . Variation of shear stress across the jth ply then becomes

$$\tau_{xz_{j+1}} - \tau_{xz_j} = I_{xz_j} \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be written for a number of adjacent plies. These plies would include either all plies in cases where no delamination occurs, or for adjacent plies between a free surface and a delaminated interface. The equations have the matrix form for n layers

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & \dots & -1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tau_{xz_2} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \tau_{xz_n} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{xz_1} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ I_{xz_n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The equations in (3) represent n equations in n-1 unknown transverse shear stresses at the layer interfaces. Utilizing a least squares orthonormalization procedure, (3) is solved for transverse shear stresses at layer interfaces. A similar set of equations are solved for the τ_{yz} stresses. This approach allows zero shear stress boundary conditions to be satisfied at the outer laminate surfaces and at interior delaminated interfaces in determining whether or not stress failure criteria have been violated. Of course, this affects variation in shear stiffness properties as damage progresses.

While the numerical results presented herein are based on the previously presented strategies, a brief note on current efforts at developing an improved methodology. Rather than simply

reducing stiffness properties to zero based on stress criteria, material properties can be related to an internal state "damage" variable. As an example, a linearly varying transverse modulus in a given ply might have the form

$$E_{22} = (1-D) E_{22}^0 \quad (4)$$

where E_{22}^0 represents the undamaged moduli and the damage parameter "D" varies from the value zero with no damage to one when the stiffness is lost. The damage parameter would be based on experimental results and would depend on observations of damage development as a function of normal and shearing strains and on ply constraints. Of course, a linear representation of the type given in equation (4) is given as an example. Higher ordered representations may be in order, see Engblom (11). Part of the problem involved developing a relationship between experimentally measured laminate damage and the equivalent moduli changes at the ply level. This relationship is essential in developing a generally applicable modeling capability. Research efforts also involve including a relationship between the level of damping and damage in a laminated structure. The approach presently being considered would be a much more global representation of changes in damping due to damage, i.e., treatment at the laminate rather than ply level.

3. EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

Experimental results are presently being generated but are not complete enough at this point to have developed an improved numerical formulation. The experiments include a sequence of tests on various laminate geometries, in which different levels of damage are developed under varying loads. To date these loads have been statically applied; however, impact tests are also scheduled. Damaged specimens are subjected to broadband sinusoidal excitation to relate level/type of damage to changes in dynamic characteristics. Specimen types to be considered include tension/compression beam-like specimens, plate and tube specimens to be impact tested, and Arcan specimens. Edge replications, x-radiography, ultrasonics and scanning electron microscopy are being utilized to quantify damage modes. One interesting aspect of the initial experimentation has been that damage can easily propagate unsymmetrically even in symmetric laminates loaded in tension. This needs to be accounted for in

relating measured laminate damage to that at the ply level.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The examples presented demonstrate the extent to which the residual properties of a laminate can vary as a result of damage caused by transient dynamic loading. Even though the numerical treatment of damage can be improved upon, the results certainly demonstrate that changes in dynamic characteristics can be very significant. These characteristics include both transient response amplitudes as well as modal properties.

Examples include the transient loading of a simply supported beam with a central load. The beams have symmetric cross-plyed layups. The loading consists of a rectangular pulse, the duration of which is assumed roughly equal to 1/2 the period of the first "undamaged" mode. Eight quadrilateral shear-deformable elements (9,10) are used to model the beam. Aspect ratios, i.e., beam length to thickness, of $L/H = 5$ and 10 are considered. Examples also include simply supported square plates of aspect ratio, i.e., width to thickness, of $A/H = 5$ and 10 as with the beams. A quadrant of the plate is modeled in each case using a 3 element by 3 element mesh. The plate loading consists of a rectangular pressure pulse loading with a uniform distribution. Material properties are assumed to be those of an E-Glass epoxy with specific moduli and strengths given as

E_x	=	60.67	GPA
E_y	=	24.82	GPA
ν_{xy}	=	0.23	
G_{xy}	=	12.00	GPA
X	=	1289	MPA
X'	=	820.0	MPA
Y	=	46.0	MPA
Y'	=	174.4	MPA
S	=	44.8	MPA

where E_x , E_y , and G_{xy} are the longitudinal, transverse and in-plane shear moduli for a ply. Transverse shear moduli are assumed to be equal to the in-plane moduli. ν_{xy} is the Poisson's ratio, X and X' are the tensile and compressive strengths in the fiber direction, Y and Y' are the transverse strengths in tension and compression, and S represents the shear strength value.

Case 1. $[90^0, 0^0]$ Laminated Beam, $L/H = 10$

In this case, a moderately thick beam is subjected to a centrally applied rectangular pulse load. Matrix cracking in the outer plies has a dominant effect on the response. This cracking initiates in the center of the beam and propagates toward the simple supports. When cracking occurs, the flexural stiffness of the beam is significantly affected as reflected in the effect on transient response. Resulting displacement and stress response is given in Figures (1) and (2) and frequency shifts are given in Table (1). The lower natural frequencies exhibit shifts of from 30 to 50% in this case. While not presented here, similar results have been obtained for beams of lower aspect ratios and the results exhibit combinations of both delamination and intralaminar matrix cracking.

Case 2. $[0^0, 90^0]$ Square Laminated Plate, $A/H = 5$

Results are given in Figures (3) and (4) for the displacement response at the center of the plate and for the maximum outer fiber stress (0^0 direction), respectively. In these plate solutions, the residual stiffness is simply set equal to zero. Differences in displacement and stress response are clearly demonstrated. Damage involves progression of matrix cracking from the corner of the plate, where in-plane shear stresses are high, to the center of the plate. Frequency shifts are given in Table (2) indicating a maximum reduction in natural frequency of about 13%.

Case 3. $[0^0, 90^0]$ Square Laminated Plate, $A/H = 10$

Similar to the previous case, displacement and stress results are presented in Figures (5) and (6). Frequency shifts are given in Table (3). Note that the results are similar to those obtained in the previous case.

5. CONCLUSIONS

As demonstrated, the effects of delamination and matrix cracking can greatly affect both the residual properties and response characteristics of laminated composites structures. The relationship between these effects and the various damage modes needs to be developed and verified through experiment. The experimental efforts discussed herein are continuing and, hopefully, will contribute to the development of a more tractable damage model formulation. Improvements in damage models would have great utility in accurately relating residual

properties to structural integrity, and as such could greatly contribute to the development of nondestructive evaluation techniques and to damage assessment sensing systems for primary load carrying laminated composite structures.

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Fig. 1. Displacement (Case 1)

Fig. 2. Stress (Case 1)

Fig. 3. Displacement (Case 2)

Fig. 4. Stress (Case 2)

Fig. 5. Displacement (Case 3)

Fig. 6. Stress (Case 3)

	BEFORE DAMAGE f0 (HZ)	DAMAGE B0 fb0 (HZ)	DAMAGE B1 fb1 (HZ)	SHIFT (fb0-f0)/f0 %	SHIFT (fb1-f0)/f0 %
1	603	307	326	-49.09	-45.94
2	2,320	1,195	1,284	-48.49	-44.66
3	4,046	2,590	2,789	-35.99	-31.07
4	4,942	3,433	3,461	-30.53	-29.97
5	8,258	4,416	4,734	-46.52	-42.67
6	12,138	6,602	7,061	-45.61	-41.83

Table 1. Frequency Shifts for [90,0]s, L/H=10, Beam

	BEFORE DAMAGE f0 (HZ)	AFTER DAMAGE B0 fb0 (HZ)	SHIFT (fb0-f0)/f0 %
1	1,912	1,735	-9.26
2	6,900	6,020	-12.75
3	7,995	7,933	-0.78
4	11,048	10,274	-7.00
5	12,078	11,785	-2.43

Table 2. Frequency Shifts for [0,90]s, A/H=5, Square Plate

	BEFORE DAMAGE f0 (HZ)	AFTER DAMAGE B0 fb0 (HZ)	SHIFT (fb0-f0)/f0 %
1	1,040	940	-9.62
2	4,349	3,766	-13.41
3	5,415	5,372	-0.79
4	7,807	7,214	-7.60
5	10,273	8,723	-15.09

Table 3. Frequency Shifts for [0,90], A/H=10, Square Plate